

KINETICS OF THE REACTION BETWEEN IODINE AND MALONIC ACID

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The reaction between malonic acid and iodine, dissolved in a solution of potassium iodide, has been investigated kinetically at 65° and at 75°. It is found to be bimolecular with respect to iodine and monomolecular with respect to malonic acid. Addition of hydrochloric acid retards the reaction, indicating that the malonate ion is the real reactant. Potassium iodide diminishes the reaction rate by lowering the concentration of "free" iodine. From this study, it is concluded that the reaction does not involve any prototropic change, similar to that accepted in the case of the corresponding reaction between bromine and malonic acid.

Meyer (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 2864) made a kinetic study of the reaction between bromine and malonic acid and found the reaction to be unimolecular and independent of the concentration of bromine. He therefore concluded that the rate-determining reaction was the enolization,

subsequent reactions being extremely rapid compared to this.

West (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1277) considered Meyer's conclusions to be based on insufficient data and repeated the work in aqueous solution at 0° in greater detail. He observed that hydrobromic acid was without any influence on the rate of the reaction and suggested that the reaction took place in two stages. Monobromomalonic acid is first formed as a result of a unimolecular reaction, similar to that proposed by Meyer (*loc. cit.*). The second stage consists of a rapid enolization, followed by a measurable bimolecular reaction between the monobromomalonic acid and bromine. He explains this by putting forth the view that the strain at the central carbon atom due to bromine favours enolization, and for the same reason it is difficult to introduce the second bromine atom. Therefore, bromination of the monobromo-acid is a slow bimolecular reaction,

He followed the reaction colorimetrically, as direct volumetric estimation of bromine was rendered impossible due to a reaction of potassium iodide with the bromomalonic acid.

The work of West has received wide attention on account of the fact that it suggests the possibility of prototropy in the case of a dicarboxylic acid like malonic acid.

The prototropic change should likewise be detectable in the corresponding reaction between iodine and malonic acid. This reaction, however, has not been investigated to the same extent. Nylen (*Kgl. Norske Videnskab. Selskabs. Skrifter* 1938, No. 2, p 19) has observed that at p_H less than 1, practically no iodine reacts with malonic acid, but at p_H greater than 5, the theoretical amount of iodine for the following reaction is used up:

To avoid the possibility of the formation of diiodomalonic acid, monoalkylmalonic acids were used. All the reactions were found to be unimolecular. Determination of the rate of reduction of diiodomalonic acid with iodide ion showed this reaction also to be unimolecular, and this was taken as a proof for the above reaction.

The literature does not contain any reference to the isolation of monoiodomalonic acid; but diiodomalonic acid was prepared by Willstätter (*Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 1374) through iodination with iodine and iodic acid in presence of cold formic acid. It decomposes very readily to give iodoacetic acid.

The present investigation was undertaken in order to elucidate the mechanism of iodination of malonic acid, particularly with a view to ascertaining any similarity of the course of the reaction with the bromination.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were of A. R. quality. The solutions were prepared in distilled water. Malonic acid solution was prepared by dissolving a known quantity of the pure, dry acid in water and making up the volume to a definite amount. The strength was further checked by titration against standard alkali, using phenolphthalein as an indicator. The strength of the iodine solution was determined by titration against a standard solution of sodium thiosulphate.

A few test runs showed that malonic acid reacted very slowly with iodine, dissolved in a solution of potassium iodide, at room temperature (30°), but at 60° - 70° , the reaction proceeded at a rate which could conveniently be measured. The reactants were contained in a closed flask, which was immersed in a thermostat maintained at a steady temperature (within $\pm 0.1^{\circ}$). The reaction was followed up by withdrawing from time to time 25 c.c. of the solution into a large excess of cold water in order to "freeze" the reaction and then immediately titrating the residual iodine against a standard solution of sodium thiosulphate, using starch as an indicator.

Preliminary Experiments to determine the Nature of the Reaction

(f) In experiments with concentrated solutions of malonic acid and iodine, we observed, even on prolonged heating at 60° - 70° , that it was not possible to ascertain the amount of iodine used up by a given quantity of malonic acid, due to the fact that with the accumulation of iodomalonic acid in sufficient quantity in the mixture, the subsequent decarboxylation of this acid and the reaction of the resulting iodoacetic acid with iodide ion (Nylén, *loc. cit.*) began to make themselves felt. This complication, however, was not manifest if we started with solutions containing relatively very small concentrations of iodine, for example, 0.05*M*-malonic acid and 0.005*M*-iodine. In such solutions, decolorisation of iodine takes place in some hours at 60° - 70° and it is possible to follow the reaction kinetically, since the subsequent reactions of decomposition products are extremely slow and do not interfere with a kinetic study of iodination at such dilutions.

(ii). The rate of disappearance of iodine is diminished by the presence of hydrochloric acid. This militates against the idea of any prototropic change in the malonic acid.

(iii). The addition of potassium iodide also retards the reaction, showing that the real reactant is "free" iodine, as in the case of most halogenation reactions.

Kinetics

The order of the reaction with respect to iodine was determined at 60° by keeping the initial concentration of malonic acid very large in comparison with that of iodine. A typical set of values thus obtained is given below (Table I).

TABLE I

0.05*M*-Malonic acid, 0.005*M*-total iodine,
0.03688*M*•KI; 25 c.c. for each titration.

Temp. = 60°

Time.	Titre values.	K_{uni} .	K_{bi} .
0 min.	23.95	...	...
30	21.45	0.003678	0.8110
60	19.4	0.003512	0.8160
90	17.6	0.003425	0.8369
120	15.4	0.003155	0.8279
230	12.35	0.002880	0.8526
320	10.2	0.002667	0.8794
410	8.45	0.002612	0.9340

TABLE II

Temp. = 60°. 0.02*M*-HCl.

Rest, same as in Table I.

Time.	*Titre values.	K_{uni} .	K_{bi} .
0 min.	23.7	...	...
30	22.55	0.001650	0.3587
60	21.3	0.001777	0.3962
90	20.4	0.001665	0.3793
120	19.55	0.001604	0.3732
180	17.95	0.001543	0.3755
240	16.65	0.001471	0.3723
360	14.5	0.001365	0.3719
485	12.65	0.001294	0.3801

Expressed as c.c. of 0.01*N*-thiosulphate.

Mean 0.3759

From Table I, it is seen that the unimolecular coefficient, K_{uni} , goes on diminishing with progress of time, whereas the bimolecular one, although showing a tendency to rise later with progress of the reaction, is much more steady, especially on the addition of hydrochloric acid (vide Table II).

Figures in Table II show that hydrochloric acid, added initially to the reaction mixture, slows down the reaction considerably, whereas, if a prototropic change were involved, the effect should have been quite the other way.

Good termolecular constants were obtained when the initial concentrations of the two reactants were kept equal (vide Table III).

TABLE III

0.005*M*-Malonic acid, 0.005*M*-total iodine, 0.025*M*•HCl, 0.04*M*-KI; 25 c.c. for each titration. Temp. = 70°

Time.	Titre values. (c.c. of 0.01 <i>N</i> -thiosulphate)	K_{ter} .
0 min.	24.25	...
60	22.5	57.225
100	21.5	57.850
152	20.4	57.750
220	19.2	57.525
260	18.45	59.475

Mean 57.965

Hence, the order of the reaction appears to be 2 with respect to iodine and 1 with respect to malonic acid, making the reaction a third order one. The obvious inference is that no prototropic change is involved and that diiodomalonic acid is straightaway formed and not through the initial formation of monoiodomalonic acid. This also explains why the monoiodo-acid has not been isolated thus far.

In order to study the effect of addition of hydrochloric acid more fully, a series of experiments were carried out with different concentrations of hydrochloric acid, keeping those of the reactants and potassium iodide the same for all the runs. The results are summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV

0.05M-Malonic acid, 0.005M-total iodine and 0.03688M-KI for all the experiments.

Temp. = 60°.

[HCl] (Conc. of HCl)	$\frac{1}{[\text{HCl}]}$	k_{obs} (observed bimol. const.)	$\frac{k_{\text{obs}}}{1/[\text{HCl}]} \times 10^3$
M/100	100	0.5560	5.6
M/60	60	0.4312	7.2
M/50	50	0.3759	7.5
M/40	40	0.3230	8.1
M/30	30	0.2537	8.4
M/20	20	0.1554	7.8
M/10	10	0.0776	7.8

The diminution of the reaction rate with increasing concentration of hydrochloric acid shows the real reactant to be the malonate ion, $\text{HOOC}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{COO}^-$, rather than the undissociated acid itself. If this be the case, then

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k \cdot [A] [C_r]^2,$$

where $[A]$ denotes concentration of the malonate ion and $[C_r]$ that of the "free" iodine.

But
$$[A] = \frac{K \cdot [\text{HA}]}{[\text{H}^+]},$$

where K is the primary dissociation constant of malonic acid.

Therefore, substituting for $[A]$, we get

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k \cdot \frac{K \cdot [\text{HA}]}{[\text{H}^+]} \cdot [C_r]^2.$$

We must express $[C_r]$ in terms of $[C_T]$, (concentration of total iodine), since it is the latter quantity that we measure in our experiments.

$$\therefore [\text{KI}_3] = \frac{[\text{KI}][\text{I}_2]}{K'},$$

where K' is the triiodide equilibrium constant.

But

$$\begin{aligned} [C_7] &= [C_7] + [KI_2], \\ &= [C_7] \cdot \left(\frac{K' + [KI]}{K'} \right). \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore [C_7] = [C_7] \cdot \left(\frac{K'}{K' + [KI]} \right).$$

$$\therefore \frac{dx}{dt} = k \left(\frac{K \cdot [HA]}{[H^+]} \right) \left(\frac{K'}{K' + [KI]} \right) [C_7]^2 \quad \dots (1)$$

In the series of experiments mentioned in Table IV, the concentration of malonic acid was kept high in comparison with that of the total iodine. Therefore, $[HA]$ may be assumed to be constant. Similarly, $[KI]$ and $[H^+]$ are constants.

$$\therefore \frac{dx}{dt} = k_{obs} \cdot [C_7]^2, \quad k_{obs} \text{ denoting the observed bimolecular constant.}$$

$$\therefore k_{obs} = k \left(\frac{K \cdot [HA]}{[H^+]} \right) \left(\frac{K'}{K' + [KI]} \right)^2 = \text{say } \frac{k'}{[H^+]}, \quad \dots (2)$$

where $k' = k \cdot K \cdot [HA] \cdot \left[\frac{K'}{K' + [KI]} \right]^2$.

Hence, if k_{obs} be plotted against $\frac{1}{[H^+]}$, a straight line, passing through the origin should be obtained, whose slope = k' . Since $[H^+]$ is practically the same as $[HCl]$, especially for concentrations of hydrochloric acid greater than $M/60$, $1/[HCl]$ can be plotted instead of $1/[H^+]$ in our case.

Fig. 1

The plot of k_{obs} against $1/[HCl]$ from values given in Table IV is actually found to be a straight line, passing through the origin (Fig. 1), thus proving the validity of equation (2). As may be expected, there is a deviation from the straight line relationship for the smaller concentrations of hydrochloric acid (less than $M/60$), since in these cases, the relation $[HCl] = [H^+]$ obviously does not hold good in the presence of $M/20$ malonic acid. Moreover, the value of K , the dissociation constant of malonic acid, calculated from the slope of the graph and the initial value of K_M in Table I, is found to be approximately 2×10^{-8} , which has the same order as that recorded in the literature (1.6×10^{-8}).

We next performed an experiment at the same temperature (60°), using a mixture containing an equivalent amount of sodium hydrogen malonate ($0.05M$) instead of the malonic acid, the concentrations of potassium iodide ($0.0369M$) and of iodine ($0.005M$) being the same as in Tables I, II and IV. Most of the iodine disappeared almost instantaneously, thus showing conclusively that the real reactant is the malonate ion, $HOOC.CH_2.COO^-$, and not the undissociated acid.

The effect of the addition of potassium iodide was then studied at 60° . Our results are summarised in Table V.

TABLE V

0.05M-Malonic acid, 0.005M total iodine and 0.025M-HCl in all the experiments.

Temperature = 60° .

[KI] (g. mols. per litre).	[KI] ² .	k_{obs} . (observed bimol const.)	$\frac{1}{k_{obs}}$
0.0223	0.0004943	0.4762	2.1020
0.03694	0.001365	0.3230	3.0960
0.04	0.0016	0.2861	3.4900
0.06	0.0036	0.1310	7.464
0.08	0.0064	0.0795	12.584
0.10	0.0100	0.0507	19.744
0.12	0.0144	0.03618	26.200

From these results it is evident that only the "free" iodine takes part in the reaction.

Equation (1) is

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k \cdot \left(\frac{K \cdot [HA]}{[H^+]} \right) \left(\frac{K'}{K' + [KI]} \right)^2 [C_7]^2.$$

Since $[HA]$, $[H^+]$ and $[KI]$ are kept high in comparison with $[C_7]$ (Table V), we have

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_{obs} \cdot [C_7]^2.$$

$$\therefore k_{obs} = \left(\frac{k \cdot K \cdot [HA]}{[H^+]} \right) \left(\frac{K'}{K' + [KI]} \right)^2 \dots \dots (3)$$

$$= \text{say } C \cdot \left(\frac{K'}{K' + [KI]} \right)^2, \text{ where } C = \frac{k \cdot K \cdot [HA]}{[H^+]}$$

$$\therefore \frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{(K' + [KI])^2}{C \cdot K'^2} = \frac{1}{C} + \frac{2[KI]}{C \cdot K'} + \frac{[KI]^2}{C \cdot K'^2}.$$

Now, K' is of the order of 10^{-3} and $[KI]$ of the order, 10^{-1} to 10^{-2} . Therefore, the second term on the right hand side can be neglected in comparison with the last term.

Hence we can write

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{C} + \frac{[KI]^2}{C \cdot K'^2}$$

The plot of $1/k_{obs}$ against $[KI]^2$ at a fixed temperature should therefore be a straight line and this is actually found to be so when the values given in Table V are plotted

(Fig. 2). The intercept = $\frac{1}{C}$ and slope = $\frac{1}{C \cdot K'^2}$.

From this graph, the value of K' at 60° was calculated and found to be approximately 13×10^{-3} . This value is about ten times that recorded in the literature. This discrepancy can be accounted for to an extent on the basis that a slight variation in the intercept causes a tremendous change in the value of K' . For obvious reasons, the experiments cannot be carried out at concentrations of potassium iodide less than that required to keep the iodine in solution, and thus a certain amount of error is introduced in the extrapolation.

Temperature Coefficient of the Velocity of Reaction

TABLE VI

0.05M-Malonic acid, 0.005M-total iodine and 0.025M-hydrochloric acid in all the experiments.

[KI] (g mol./litre).	$k_{obs.}$ (60°).	$k_{obs.}$ (70°)	Ratio $\frac{k_{obs.} (70^\circ)}{k_{obs.} (60^\circ)}$
0.02223	0.4752	2.112	3.04
0.03694	0.3230	1.078	3.37
0.04	0.2861	0.935	3.39
0.06	0.1343	0.4420	3.52
0.05	0.0795	0.2766	3.56
0.10	0.0507	0.1801	3.59
0.12	0.03618	0.1313	3.65
0.00 (by extrapolation)			2.0

* From plots of $\frac{1}{k_{obs}}$ against $[KI]^2$.

Table VI gives the results of experiments, carried out with reaction mixtures containing 0.05M-malonic acid, 0.005M-iodine, 0.025M-hydrochloric acid and varying amounts of potassium iodide at 60° and 70° . The last column in the table gives the ratios,

$$\frac{k_{obs.} (70^\circ)}{k_{obs.} (60^\circ)}$$

calculated from the plots τ/k_{obs} against $[\text{KI}]^2$ at these two temperatures (Fig. 2). The

variation in the temperature of coefficient with the concentration of potassium iodide would be readily understood by a reference to equation (3), which shows that k_{obs} includes

$$k_{\text{int}} \cdot \left(\frac{K \cdot [\text{HA}]}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) \left(\frac{K'}{K' + [\text{KI}]} \right)^2.$$

The value of k_{obs} extrapolated to zero concentration of potassium iodide gives a temperature coefficient of 2. Even this includes, in this particular set of experiments, the ratio of

$$\left(\frac{K \cdot [\text{HA}]}{[\text{H}^+]} \right)$$

at the two temperatures. Consequently, when corrections are introduced for this, we would get a temperature coefficient even lower than 2 for the actual termolecular velocity coefficient—a very natural value for a third order reaction.